

First Dissociation Constant of Phosphoric Acid at a Number of Temperatures

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The pK_1 values of H_3PO_4 from 273.15 to 323.15 K have been recalculated from Nims as well as Bates data with the help of modified Davies equation. The difference in the pK_1 values has been largely reconciled. At 308.15 K, pK_1 has also been measured using Na-salt instead of K-salt. There is almost no difference in the values of pK_1 found. Bates had come to the conclusion that cells similar to Nims, where $m_{KH_2PO_4} : m_{HCl}$ lie between 1 and 3, or when pH is < 3.0 , do not give accurate pK_1 values. Using modified Davies equation, cells with pH values < 3.0 gave reliable pK_1 values.

THERE are only a few reports on the determination of pK_1 of phosphoric acid at a number of temperatures by e.m.f. method using cells without liquid junction potential. Nims¹ determined pK_1 of phosphoric acid using cell (C-1) with three series of solutions having

$m_1/m_2 = 2.071, 3.102$ and 3.079 and μ between 0.01 and 0.10 mol kg^{-1} . He used equation (1) to get pK_1 at $273.45, 288.65, 298.15, 310.65$ and 323.15 K , where $\mu = m_1 + m_H$.

$$-\log m_H - \log \left(\frac{m_1}{m_2 - m_1} - 1 \right) + 2A\sqrt{\mu} = pK_1 + B\mu \quad (1)$$

Here B is an empirical constant whose value differed with the ratio $m_1 : m_2$.

Bates² used the same cell (C-1) and determined pK_1 from 273.15 to 333.15 K in steps of 5 K using five series of solutions having $m_1/m_2 = 1.2414, 1.2683, 1.5581, 2.1840$ and 6 and μ lying between 0.02 to 0.4 mol kg^{-1} . He defined a term pWH given in equation (2).

$$pWH = -\log \gamma_H \gamma_{Cl} m_H = \frac{(E - E^\circ)F}{2.3026 RT} + \log m_{Cl} \quad (2)$$

So pK_1 is given by equation (3).

$$pK_1 = pWH + \log \frac{m_{H_2PO_4}}{m_{H_2PO_4}} + \log \frac{\gamma_{H_2PO_4} \gamma_{Cl}}{\gamma_{H_2PO_4}} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \text{where, } m_{H_2PO_4} &= m_2 - m_H \\ m_{H_2PO_4} &= m_1 - m_2 + m_H \end{aligned} \right\} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

For use in equation (4) the value of m_H was obtained either from a provisional dissociation

constant and applying the law of mass action and a method of successive approximation, or from pWH using equation (2). Since it is not possible to obtain an exact value of $\gamma_H \gamma_{Cl}$, Bates defined an apparent m_H , namely m_H' and assumed that at low μ , $m_H = m_H'$ and is given by equation (5).

$$-\log m_H' = pWH - \frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + B_a^2 \mu} \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

So, apparent $\log K_1$ or $\log K_1'$ is given by equation (6).

$$pK_1' = pWH + \log \frac{m_2 - m_H'}{m_1 - m_2 + m_H'} \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

The values of pK_1' were plotted against μ , and the intercepts of the plots at $\mu = 0$ gave pK_1 . Values of pK_1 thus obtained differed with the series used. This led Bates to conclude that accurate values of pK_1 could not be determined when $1 < m_1/m_2 < 3$ and $pH < 3.0$.

Bates then worked with cell (C-2). Using two

series of solutions having $m_1/m_2 = 5$ and 8 and a different method of calculation he determined pK_1 of phosphoric acid from 273.15 to 333.15 K in steps of 5 K .

The values of pK_1 thus found by Bates differ from the pK_1 values of Nims [obtained with cell (C-1) using a different method of calculation] by 0.024 at 298.15 K and 0.017 at 323.15 K ,—the only two temperatures common to both the workers.

We have recalculated pK_1 from the e.m.f. data of Bates with cell (C-1) using modified Davies equation³ to see whether accurate values of pK_1 could be obtained from his cell (C-1). We have

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TABLE 3—E.M.F. AND THE MOLALITIES OF IONS IN CELL (C-4) at 308.15 K

${}^m\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4$ (m_1)	${}^m\text{HCl}$ (m_2)	E/abs. volt	${}^m\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4$	${}^m\text{H}$	${}^m\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4$ (x)	$\mu = m_1 + m_2 - x$	$\log K_{A(1)} - \frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}}$
0.029374	0.010221	0.50052	0.022131	0.002978	0.007242	0.032353	3.801
0.037003	0.012909	0.49250	0.027370	0.003275	0.009633	0.040279	3.796
0.044512	0.015522	0.48620	0.032519	0.003529	0.011993	0.048042	3.794
0.053307	0.018225	0.48087	0.037761	0.003744	0.014480	0.057052	3.792
0.058896	0.020547	0.47685	0.042269	0.003920	0.016627	0.062816	3.791
0.067638	0.023241	0.47297	0.047448	0.004069	0.019171	0.070708	3.786
0.080348	0.028385	0.46625	0.056349	0.004385	0.023999	0.084734	3.779
0.086705	0.031000	0.46303	0.060278	0.004572	0.026427	0.091278	3.778

All concentrations and ionic strengths are in mol kg⁻¹.TABLE 4— pK_1 AND β_1 AT 308.15 K

Cell	pK_1	$\beta_1/\text{mol}^{-1}\text{kg}$
(C-1) with KH_2PO_4 and hydrogen electrode (recalculated).	2.195 ± 0.0032	0.35 ± 0.068
(C-4) with NaH_2PO_4 and hydrogen electrode.	2.187 ± 0.0016	0.39 ± 0.025

In modified Davies equation β should be independent of the composition of ionic atmosphere unless it is drastically changed. To see this we set up cell (C-4), given later, at 308.15 K only.

Experimental

$\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (AnalaR, B.D.H.) was found to be 99.98% pure when analysed by standard method⁷. A G.R., S.M., sample of HCl was diluted with water to sp. gr. 1.10 and fractionally distilled. The middle fraction, free from bromide⁸, was collected and analysed separately against pure AgNO_3 and pure borax by standard methods⁹. A stock solution of $\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and HCl in the approximate molal ratio of 3 : 1 was prepared from which the experimental solutions were obtained by suitable dilution with double-distilled water. The stoichiometric concentrations were correct to one micromol kg⁻¹. All weighings were corrected for buoyancy. Preparation of electrodes, filling up of cells, thermostat, potentiometer assembly etc were as reported earlier¹⁰. The e.m.f. of the duplicate (C-4) cells agreed within 0.06 mV. The recorded e.m.f. values of Table 3 are the mean of the two readings after applying correction for barometric pressure, vapour pressure and bubbler depth¹¹.

Results and Discussion

The e.m.f. of cell (C-4), is given by equation

(8), and equations (9) to (12) are valid in this case also. The experimental e.m.f. values after correction, and the L.H.S. of equation (12) are recorded in Table 3. Here $m_1/m_2 = 3$ approximately and the pH of the buffer < 3.0. The plot of L.H.S. of equation (12) against μ obtained with cell (C-4) is linear.

Table 4 records the pK_1 and β_1 values obtained by us from cells (C-4) and (C-1). It will be seen from Table 4 that pK_1 values obtained with cell (C-4) are within 0.008 units of that recalculated from Bates cell (C-1) though pH of the cell solutions are < 3.0. The values of β_1 in the two cases are within ±0.02 mol⁻¹kg. Our experiment as well as recalculating indicates that modified Davies equation can fruitfully be employed to give accurate values of pK_1 even below pH 3.0 and both the cells (C-1) and (C-4) are capable of giving accurate pK_1 values.

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